

Digitaltag 2021

Data (Horror) Escape Room

Einfache Sprache | Barrierefreiheit | Anfänger im Netz

Digitaltag
2021

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Digital Shift! Forschen in der digitalen Welt und der 'Data Escape Room' (ein Spiel).

- Data Horror Escape Room 2020 [CC-BY-SA-4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)
<https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home?authuser=0>

Play the Game! - Data Horror Escape Room

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Data Horror Escape Room

Home About this website

Welcome

Dear Guest,

Welcome to our Escape Room. We are so happy to see you here!

Below you will find the link ENTER to start the game.

Rules

- Just like in a physical escape room, you do not need any search engines. If you do need something outside of this escape room, we will provide a link to it.
- This escape room is meant to be a playful exercise; please don't break anything or use brute force to solve a puzzle.
- This escape room can be completed in roughly 1 hour.
- If you dare, feel free to invite others to enter the Data Horror Escape Room.

Tips

<https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home>

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You push against the door – it creaks open slowly giving you a glimpse into the room. There's a desk light on, and it looks like someone was there maybe a moment ago, but as the door fully opens, still no-one speaks... so you gingerly step inside.

Professor Hutseephnuts doesn't appear to be there. Maybe you should just leave.

But suddenly, the door shuts behind you with a loud bang followed by a series of clicks. Did the door just lock itself shut? If so, you're trapped in the office. What do you do?

<https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home>

The [Data Horror Escape Room](https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home) was a collaboration between Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Lena Karvovskaya and Elisa Rodenburg), Leiden University Libraries (Joanne Yeomans), and Eindhoven University of Technology (Anne Aarts and Bart Aben):
<https://sites.google.com/vu.nl/datahorror/home>